

Supplementary Nomenclature for Stage-Wise Dataset Generation for Two-Stage Security-Constrained AC Optimal Power Flow

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This online companion document provides the complete nomenclature for the associated conference paper. The nomenclature is provided separately due to the page limit of the main paper.

NOMENCLATURE

A. Sets and indices

d, Ω_m^d	Index and set of demands located at bus m .
e, Ω_m^e	Index and set of storage units located at bus m .
g, Ω_m^g	Index and set of conventional generators located at bus m .
m, n	Indices of buses in the transmission network.
s	Index of real-time scenarios.
w, Ω_m^w	Index and set of wind plants located at bus m .
Φ_m	Set of buses linked to bus m by transmission lines in the base network.
$\phi_{m,s}$	Set of buses linked to bus m by transmission lines in scenario s after the realized outage.

B. Parameters

a_g, b_g, c_g	Quadratic cost coefficients of generator g , [€/MWh ²], [€/MWh], and [€].
C_d^{shed}	Load shedding penalty cost for demand d , [€/MWh].
$C_e, C_e^\uparrow, C_e^\downarrow$	Discharge cost and DA upward/downward reserve availability costs of storage unit e , [€/MWh], [€/MWh/h].
C_e^+, C_e^-	RT upward and downward regulation costs of storage unit e , [€/MWh].
$C_g^\uparrow, C_g^\downarrow$	DA upward and downward reserve availability costs of generator g , [€/MWh/h].
C_g^+, C_g^-	RT upward and downward regulation costs of generator g , [€/MWh].
C_w^{curt}	Wind curtailment penalty cost of wind plant w , [€/MWh].
$\underline{\Delta}_m, \overline{\Delta}_m$	Minimum and maximum voltage angle at bus m , [rad].
$\Delta w_{w,s}$	Wind power deviation of plant w in scenario s from its DA forecast, [MW].
η_e^d	Discharging efficiency of storage unit e .
P_d, Q_d	Active and reactive power demand of load d , [MW] and [MVar].
$\text{pf}_d^f, \text{pf}_w^f$	Reactive power factor coefficients of demand d and wind plant w .
$\overline{E}_e^{\text{av}}$	Available energy in storage unit e , [MWh].
$\underline{P}_g, \overline{P}_g$	Minimum and maximum active power output of generator g , [MW].

$\underline{Q}_g, \overline{Q}_g$	Minimum and maximum reactive power output of generator g , [MVar].
$\overline{R}_g^D, \overline{R}_g^U$	Maximum downward and upward reserve capacities of generator g , [MW].
$\overline{S}_{m,n}^f, \overline{s}_{m,n,s}^f$	Base-case and scenario-dependent apparent power flow limits of line (m, n) , [MVA].
$\underline{V}_m, \overline{V}_m$	Minimum and maximum voltage magnitudes at bus m , [p.u.].
W_w	DA forecasted active power injection of wind plant w , [MW].
$Y_{m,n}^L, Y_{m,n}^{\text{Sh}}$	Magnitudes of series and shunt admittances of line (m, n) in the base network, [p.u.].
$\Theta_{m,n}^L, \Theta_{m,n}^{\text{Sh}}$	Angles of series and shunt admittances of line (m, n) in the base network, [rad].
$y_{m,n,s}^L, y_{m,n,s}^{\text{Sh}}$	Magnitudes of series and shunt admittances of line (m, n) in scenario s , [p.u.].
$\theta_{m,n,s}^L, \theta_{m,n,s}^{\text{Sh}}$	Angles of series and shunt admittances of line (m, n) in scenario s , [rad].

C. First-stage (DA) variables

Δ_m, V_m	Voltage angle and magnitude at bus m , [rad] and [p.u.].
P_e, P_g	Scheduled power of storage unit e and generator g , [MW].
$P_{m,n}^f, Q_{m,n}^f$	Active and reactive power flow on line (m, n) , [MW] and [MVar].
Q_g, Q_w	Scheduled reactive power generation of generator g and wind plant w , [MVar].
$R_e^\uparrow, R_e^\downarrow$	Upward and downward reserve capacities procured from storage unit e , [MW].
$R_g^\uparrow, R_g^\downarrow$	Upward and downward reserve capacities procured from generator g , [MW].

D. Second-stage (RT) variables

$\delta_{m,s}, v_{m,s}$	Voltage angle and magnitude at bus m in scenario s , [rad] and [p.u.].
$P_{d,s}^{\text{shed}}, P_{w,s}^{\text{curt}}$	Load shedding and wind curtailment of demand d and wind plant w in scenario s , [MW].
$P_{m,n,s}^f, Q_{m,n,s}^f$	Active and reactive power flow on line (m, n) in scenario s , [MW] and [MVar].
$q_{w,s}$	Reactive power output of wind plant w in scenario s , [MVar].
$r_{e,s}^+, r_{e,s}^-$	Upward and downward regulation of storage unit e in scenario s , [MW].
$r_{g,s}^+, r_{g,s}^-$	Upward and downward regulation of generator g in scenario s , [MW].